

Questions For Composing - Pre Draft

What is the purpose of the piece?

- Is this piece going to have an audience?
 - If it has an audience, who will that audience be?
 - What is your intended interaction between the audience and this piece?
How important is that to you?
- Is this piece written without an audience in mind?
 - If so, in what context will anyone hear this piece?
 - Will that context dictate some of the compositional parameters?
- Is this piece written as part of or in service of another event or medium of communication/art? (i.e. movie score, incidental music for a play, ballet, mass, ceremonial music)
 - If yes, what is the role of the music in the larger context of the event?
 - How does that role set certain compositional parameters for your work?
 - How can your piece best serve that role?

What is this piece trying to express?

- Is this piece trying to express a thought, an emotion, or a combination of both?
 - If an emotion, what emotion is it trying to express? (i.e. “happy”, “sad”)
 - What music do you know that sounds like that emotion to you? (i.e. what sounds “happy” to you?)
 - What aspects of that piece best communicate that emotion to you?
 - Can you identify how that music is constructed to communicate that emotion?
 - How many different elements in the piece support this main emotional message, and how are they effective?
 - Are there aspects of this piece that you can emulate and reinterpret for your own piece?
 - If a thought, what idea is it trying to express?
 - What music do you know that communicates a similar idea?
 - What aspects of that piece best communicate that idea to you?
 - Can you identify how that music is constructed to communicate that idea?
 - How many different elements in the piece support this main idea, and how are they effective?
 - Are there aspects of this piece that you can emulate and reinterpret for your own piece?

How will this piece be performed?

- Will this be a pre-recorded performance? (pre-recorded live performers or fixed media)
 - Will this piece utilize live performers?
 - If yes, in what context will the performers be recording this work? (asynchronous, studio setting,)
 - What considerations from this context should you take into account for this piece?
 - What combination of instruments will best communicate your intended expression?
 - If not, what electronic palette will best communicate your intended expression?
- Will this be a Live Performance?
 - Will this piece utilize live performers?
 - If not, what electronic palette will best communicate your intended expression?
 - If yes, what combination of instruments will best communicate your intended expression?
 - If yes, who are the intended performers? (this can be either specific individuals or a particular ability level i.e. college level trombonist or virtuoso pianist)
 - How can you best showcase the intended performer's abilities in support of your piece's intention?
 - Are there special characteristics of that instrument that can be expressive tools towards your intention?
 - If a specific individual, what do they do exceptionally well on the instrument? Can you showcase this?
 - If yes, what venue will the piece be performed in?
 - Are there considerations for this piece from the venue to include in your planning?

Other general questions to ask

- How long do you see the piece being?
 - Will the potential length of the performance be effected by performer ability?
- What form do you envision for the piece?
 - If you dont have a form in mind already, what are some potential forms based on your already established constraints?

- About how long do you have to write the music?
- Does your music engage in some way with genre or a cultural heritage?
 - If the music engages with cultural heritage, what are the considerations you should take into account when writing music that will ensure it is respectful and in authentic relationship to this culture?
 - If the music engages in genre, what are the stylistic schema/norms/expectations of writing music in said genre? (a certain pitch language, chord progression, rhythmic hierarchy, lyrical subject material, etc.)
 - Are there clichés of this genre that you should be aware of?
 - Are there tropes that you plan to fulfill? Are there tropes that you plan to intentionally subvert? How can you accomplish this?
- What are some adjectives you would like to use to describe your finished piece?
 - What are some adjectives you would like to avoid? (keep in mind this is from your perspective, not a perceived audience.)

Answer each of the questions in prose. (i.e. “this piece will be no more than 10 minutes long,” “this piece is for string quartet,” “this piece will express happiness”, “this piece is about a love story,” “this piece engages with jazz and its cultural heritage,” etc.)

Read over your answers before you begin writing, and check back in with your answers throughout the writing process. It is more than likely that your answers to certain questions will change and that is ok. This is meant to be a tool to creating an internal dialogue that will propel the creative process forward, not to construct arbitrary statutes that are immutable once written.

Most importantly, remember that creating music to the best of your ability usually boils down to a battle with decision fatigue. Answering these questions can help make the blank page less blank, question yourself less in the actual moments of generating material, and create clarity on how to move forward in the revision process. Many composers with “natural talent” follow some version of this process intuitively, but absolutely anyone can do it intentionally and if approached with an open mind, use it to create a successful piece of music.